

DECHEMA

Gesellschaft für Chemische Technik
und Biotechnologie e.V.

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

11 - 15 Mai 2025

Bad Gögging (close to Munich) · Germany

17th PPEPPD

International Conference on Properties and Phase Equilibria for Product and Process Design

www.dechema.de/ppeppd2025

© Monarch Hotel

15.30-16.00	Coffee break
16.00-22.00	Poster Party (P1) with barbecue

Tuesday, 13. May

8.30-10.30	Invited Presentations: G. Sadowski, C. Mc Cabe Tailoring of polymer properties using thermodynamics and mechanics, Michael Fischlschweiger , TU Clausthal, Germany Extension of molecular thermodynamics to interface for confined transfer, Xiaohua Lu , Nanjing Tech University, China	
10.30-11.00	Coffee Break	
11.00 - 12.30	<p>Dynamic Processes: F. Llovell, M. Richter Mechanisms of Droplet Interaction and Interfacial Phenomena in Liquid-Liquid Systems, <u>T. Zeiner</u>¹, M. Singer¹, P. Zimmermann², ¹ KIT, Germany, ² BSH, Germany</p> <p>Gas Hydrate Formation Dynamics: Integrating Nucleation and Growth through Chemical Affinity-Based Models, <u>I. Oliveira</u>, C. Costa, A. Barreto Jr., F. Tavares, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil</p> <p>Computational Design of Peptides as Detectors, Sensors and Drugs, <u>C. Hall</u>, North Carolina State University, USA</p>	<p>Thermodynamics for Process Development: A. Soto, A.P. Fröba CO₂ hydrogenation: new high-pressure equilibrium data for technology improvement, S. Pereda, N. Cotabarrena, F.A. Sanchez, <u>P. Hegel</u>, Universidad Nacional del Sur, Argentina</p> <p>Adsorption Processes of Contaminants of Emerging Concern from Environmental Water, <u>A.B. Pereira</u>, M.C. Naranjo, J.A. Pulido, J.C. Bastos, J.M.M. Araújo, NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal</p> <p>Design of a Novel Process for the Production of Synthetic Diesel Substitutes from Formaldehyde and n-Butanol/ Isobutanol, <u>J. Burger</u>, L. Winklbauer, TUM, Germany</p>
12.30 - 14.00	Lunch	
14.00 - 19.00	Excursion to Regensburg	
19.00-20.30	Dinner	

Wednesday, 14. May

8.30-10.30	Invited Presentations: H Matsuda, J.C. Hemptiene Presentation of EFCE awardee Thermodynamics of polymeric materials for the energy transition Maria Grazia De Angelis , University of Edinburgh, UK,	
10.30-11.00	Coffee Break	
11.00 - 12.30	<p>New Model Development: M. Trusler, G.M. Kontogeorgis Thermodynamic Modeling of Rare Earth Elements: Developing Processes for Recovery from Secondary Sources, <u>G. Das</u>, A. Anderko, OLI Systems Inc., USA</p> <p>Validation of Molecular Models via Virial Coefficients and the Virial Equation of State, <u>D. Kofke</u>, R. Suresh, O. Desai, A. Schultz, University at Buffalo, USA</p> <p>A Novel Global Renormalization Group Theory Incorporating Symmetric and Asymmetric Fluctuations on a Cubic Lattice</p>	<p>Modelling: M. Fischlschweiger, F.W. Tavares Experimental characterization and thermodynamic modeling of Cryogenic sorption isotherms in amorphous polymers, <u>M. Minelli</u>, V. Signorini, G. Oleari, University of Bologna, Italy</p> <p>Evaluating Square Gradient Theory with Various Equations of State for Correlation and Prediction of Surface Tension, <u>R. Elliott</u>, KFUPM Dhahran, Saudi Arabia</p> <p>Surfing the Molecular Sea with Stochastic Machine Learning: Sigma Profiles as a Digital Chemical Space, <u>D. Abranches</u>¹, E. Maginn², Y. Colón², ¹ University of Aveiro, Portugal, ² University of Notre Dame, USA</p>

22	Estimation of interaction parameters for the Peng-Robinson equation of state using quantum chemical calculations and ANN, <u>H. Matsukawa</u> , K. Otake, Tokyo university of science, Japan
23	Prediction of excess enthalpy in binary mixtures through probabilistic matrix completion, with a GP enforced smoothness constraint, <u>G. Hermanus</u> , T. Louw, J. Cripwell, Stellenbosch University, South Africa
24	Advancing Ethanol/Water Separation in Functionalized Polymer Membranes Through Grand Canonical Monte Carlo, Molecular Dynamics, and Machine Learning-Driven Predictive Modeling, <u>A. Ordorica-Fernandez</u> ² , C. Quach ¹ , Z. Parkerson ¹ ; K Jennings ¹ ; P. Cummings ² ; C. McCabe ² , ¹ Heriot-Watt University, UK, ² Vanderbilt University, USA
	COSMO
25	Estimating Parameters of SAFT- γ Mie Equation of State Using COSMO-SAC Generated Data, <u>S.N. Boroujeni</u> , G. Seth, A. Galindo, G. Jackson, C. Adjiman, Imperial College London, UK
26	Extension of openCOSMO-RS for conformer ensembles: conformer equilibrium and its effects on thermodynamic equilibria predictions, <u>J. Otárola-Sepúlveda</u> ¹ , M. Minceva ¹ , M. Stahn ² , S. Müller ³ , I. Smirnova ³ , ¹ TUM, Germany; ² University of Bonn, Germany; ³ Hamburg University of Technology, Germany
27	Comparison of UNIFAC-LLE and COSMO-SAC Models for Liquid-Liquid Equilibria Predictions of Produced Water from Oil Systems, <u>E.R.A. Lima</u> , C.L. Silveira ² , H.C. Ferraz ³ , S.E. Weschenfelder ⁴ , ¹ Rio de Janeiro State University, Brazil, ² Federal University of Santa Maria, Brazil, ³ Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, ⁴ Petrobras, Brazil
28	General improvement of openCOSMO-RS including atomic polarizabilities calculated from first principles, D. Grigorash ¹ , <u>S. Müller</u> ² , E. Heid ³ ; F. Neese ⁴ ; D. Liakos ⁵ ; C. Riplinger ⁴ ; M. García-Ratés ⁴ ; P. Paricaud ⁶ , E.H. Stenby ¹ ; I. Smirnova ² ; W. Yan ¹ , ¹ DTU, Denmark ² TUHH, Germany; ³ TU Wien, Austria; ⁴ FAccTs GmbH, Germany; ⁵ Max Planck Institut für Kohleforschung, Germany, ⁶ Institut Polytechnique de Paris, France
	Interfacial Properties
29	Adsorption Processes of Contaminants of Emerging Concern from Environmental Water, <u>A.B. Pereira</u> , NOVA School of Science and Technology, Portugal
30	Confinement Effects in Mesopores Studied by Molecular Dynamics Simulations, <u>M. Högl</u> , H. Kraus, N. Hansen, University of Stuttgart, Germany
31	On the effect of confinement on reversible chemical reactions, <u>I. Pereira</u> ¹ , I. Segtovich ¹ , H. Pacheco ¹ , M. Castier ² , F. Tavares ¹ , ¹ Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, ² Texas A&M University at Qatar, Qatar
32	Advanced Direct Air Capture Membranes: Combining Ionic Liquid Mixtures with Nanoceramic Layers, <u>T. Makino</u> , Y. Kohno, Y. Kanasaki, T. Fujii, National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology, Japan
33	Fast and accurate adsorption calculation using the GPU-accelerated classical density functional theory for high-throughput screening and process modelling of paraffin/olefin separation, <u>T.W. Teh</u> , R. Stierle, N. Hansen, J. Gross, University Stuttgart, Germany
34	Thermal conductivity at solid/fluid interfaces: Effective thermal transport in nanoporous from microscopic mechanisms, <u>N.F. de Souza</u> ¹ , L.F.M. Franco ¹ , B. Coasne ² ; C. Herrero ³ , ¹ University of Campinas, Brasilia, ² University Grenoble Alpes, France ³ Institut Laue-Langevin, France
35	Unusual Surface Properties for the mixture of water + acetic acid, <u>F. Brettschneider</u> , S. Enders, KIT, Germany
	Aqueous Systems
36	Modeling the Solubility of Pharmaceutical Drug solutions with the SAFT- γ Mie Approach, <u>S. Paliwal</u> , A. Alyazidi, T. Bernet, A.J. Haslam, G. Jackson, A. Galindo, Imperial College London, UK
37	Thermodynamic Modeling of Electrolyte Solutions for All-Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries, <u>J. Heiß</u> , M. Kohns, RPTU Kaiserslautern, Germany
38	A Thermodynamic Based Approach for Modeling Solubility and Phase Behavior in Complex Cocrystal Systems, <u>S. Nasrallah</u> , TUM, Germany
39	Calorimetric analysis of aqueous alcohol solutions up to 450 MPa, <u>J. Troncoso</u> , Universidade de Vigo, Spain
40	Computational screening for novel aqueous amine solvents for carbon capture, <u>E. Tsochantaris</u> ¹ , K. Nehil-Puleo ² , P. Cummings ¹ , C. McCabe ¹ , Heriot-Watt University, UK
41	Comparison of Thermodynamic Modelling with Different Approaches of the Biomolecule Ionic interactions in Solutions of Two- and Three-Basic Amino Acids, their Salts and Derivatives, <u>J. Tsurko</u> , W. Kunz, University of Regensburg, Germany

Lectures

Adsorption Processes of Contaminants of Emerging Concern from Environmental Water

*Ana B. Pereira**, *María C. Naranjo*, *Jhon A. Pulido*, *Joana C. Bastos*, *João M. M. Araújo*

LAQV, REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal

*Corresponding author: anab@fct.unl.pt

Advances in separation technologies

The European projects [MAR2PROTECT](#) and [ALERT-PFAS](#), coordinated by our group, aim to remove contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) related to global and climate change. The presence of these CECs in soil, water, air and food is of concern throughout society. Among the CECs, per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS, considered “forever chemicals”), and pharmaceuticals are referred to as the families of compounds that cause the most hazardous effects in the environment. These CECs are used intensively, and their disposal is not normally done correctly. Then, the detection of these different CECs has been consistently detected in alarming concentrations. High exposure to these compounds increases the risk of dangerous health issues for humans. Remediation techniques have been demonstrated not to be useful in reducing the presence of these compounds in the environment because they are limited or inefficient or are based on incineration emitting harmful air pollutants.

This work is focused on the design (bio)materials to develop climate-friendly processes to separate PFAS and pharmaceuticals. The most appropriate (bio)materials will be custom-designed and evaluated for each specific application. Then, the development of cost-efficient technologies for the removal of contaminants of emerging concern from environmental water is optimized. The results are promising, opening a very interesting path to the optimization of a more sustainable process, which helps to solve one of the current environmental and health issues of great concern in Europe achieving a cleaner environment for the species and ensuring the well-being of species.